

ISic3331

The Syracusans honour King Gelon, son of Hieron II

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

limestone (perhaps area of Taormina?)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2013.10.03

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Ortygia, Siracusa

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 16109

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ὁ δᾶμος τῶν Συρακοσίων
2. βασιλέα Γέλωνα βασιλέος Ἰέρωνος
3. Διὶ Ἑλλανίωι

Apparatus

Text of Syll. (3rd edn) no. 428

Translation (en)

The people of the Syracusans (dedicate/honour) King Gelon, son of King Hieron
to Zeus Hellanios

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285063

EDR 114426

EDCS 64900709

Bibliography

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